

THE TASKS OF COMPARATIVE LINGUISTICS

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***Abstract.** This article provides information about the current tasks comparative linguistics in the process of language study, its brief history, components and the linguists who contributed to the development of comparative linguistics.*

***Key words:** comparative linguistics, comparative - historical linguistics, typology, contrastive linguistics, similarities and differences.*

Introduction. The Rise of the Comparative Method

Through voyages, conquests, trading, and colonialization from the sixteenth century onward, Europe became acquainted with a wide variety of languages. Information on languages from Africa, Asia, and America became available in the form of word lists, grammars, dictionaries, and religious texts, and attempts at classifying these languages followed. Large-scale word collections for language comparisons were a notable feature of the centuries after the Renaissance. Some landmarks were Konrad Gesner 1555, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz 1717, Johann Christoph Adelung 1782, 1806, Lorenzo Hervás y Panduro 1784, 1800, Peter Simon Pallas 1786, among others. These played an important role in the development of comparative linguistics.

Main Body: Why do we need comparison?

Comparison is a universal mental operation which enables us to define the similarities and difference, equality and inequality, identify and opposite. All of our knowledge is the result of comparison of different things and their properties with other similar things and their properties. In linguistics we should distinguish

internal and external comparison. External comparison means systematic comparing of two or more languages and in this cause comparison becomes a methods of linguistic investigation. Internal comparison units beginning from phonemes to text. Comparative Linguistics consists of three components – Comparative - historical linguistics, Typology and Contrastive linguistics.

The task of Comparative – historical linguistics

Comparative historical linguistics is a branch of linguistics that studies the relationships between languages and their historical development. It involves comparing languages to identify their similarities and differences, which can help reconstruct their ancestral forms and understand how they evolved over time. It is diachronic and investigates languages in these aspects: language families, phonetic, lexical, grammatical changes. the representatives of comparative historical linguistics are France Bob, Rasmus Rusk, Jacob Grimm and others who lived in the XVII - XIX centuries.

The task of Typology

The tasks of typology are as follows:

- 1) classification of the languages of the world;
- 2) to establish linguistic universals
- 3) to establish types of forms;
- 4) to work out metalanguages for comparing languages.

The representatives of Typology are V.Humboldt, A.Schleicher, J.Greenberg, Yu.V.Rozhdesvensky, B.Uspensky and others .In classification of languages different typologists precede from different linguistic features - morphological, syntactical, phonological etc. For example: B. Uspensky analyzed how language functions as a system of signs and its role in shaping cultural phenomena. Another Russian linguist is Y.V. Rozhdestvensky. He examined various language families, comparing their phonological, morphological, and syntactic structures. His research assisted refine methods for tracing the development of languages and their historical connections.

The Tasks of Contrastive Ling

In Contrastive linguistics we usually compare mother tongue and the foreign language we are learning. The Theoretical Tasks of Contrastive Linguistics:

- 1) To establish similarities and differences between the languages compared;
- 2) To fix the features of both languages escaped from the attention of linguists in the process of internal comparison of these languages;
- 3) To define the tendencies existing in both language;
- 4) To define the interlanguage equivalents;
- 5) To fix loan elements, if the languages compared are permanently in contact with each other;
- 6) To explain the reasons of the similarities and differences between the units compared as far as possible;

In Europe the earliest works on comparative linguistics appeared in XIX - XX centuries. In Central Asia the earliest work on comparative linguistics appeared in XI century. It was Diwan Lughat al - Turk (The Vocabulary of Turkic People) written by Mahmud al- Kashgari. The second earliest work on comparative linguistics in Central Asia was Muhakamat ul-Lughatayn (Thoughts on vocabularies) written by Alisher Navoi, great Uzbek poet, statesman, founder of the Uzbek literary language.

Conclusion. Comparative linguistics has played an important role in the issue of language since ancient times and it continues. It is not wrong to say that comparative linguistics is the most correct way to study the language in depth in all aspects. And this has been proven by linguists through their scientific research over the year.

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